

Intermediate quantifiers and valid syllogisms on EQ-algebras

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“This paper is dedicated to Professor Anatolij Dvurečenskij on the occasion of his 75th birthday”

Abstract

Intermediate quantifiers are expressions of natural language, for example “most, almost all, many, a few” using which we quantify a number of some objects in a given universe. We have shown in [23] that all valid syllogisms with intermediate quantifiers are a consequence of only two algebraic inequalities and one equality. The result was obtained in the formalism of Łukasiewicz fuzzy type theory whose truth values form a linearly ordered complete MV-algebra. In this paper we will prove that the same holds if we replace MV-algebra by a much more general IEQ-algebra (involutive EQ-algebra).

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1 Introduction

This paper addresses the concept of EQ-algebra as an algebraic basis of higher-order fuzzy logic called *Fuzzy Type Theory* (FTT). EQ-algebras were introduced in [18, 22] and since then studied by many authors (see [1, 3, 7, 8, 9, 27]). The motivation comes from the classical type theory in which the basic connective is equality (identity) [2, 12]. Note that the endeavor to develop logic on the basis of equality as the principal connective can be traced to G. W. Leibniz, L. Wittgenstein, and F. P. Ramsey (cf. [4, 26]).

The mathematical fuzzy logic initiated in [10] and later developed by many authors (cf. [11, 24] and the citations therein) is based on the concept of *residuated lattice* which is a lattice endowed by additional operations of *multiplication* \otimes and *residuation* \rightarrow tied by the adjointness property. The main connective in the corresponding fuzzy logic is implication and the equivalence is derived.

Thus, the following question arises: can we introduce an algebra with fuzzy equality as the main operation which would be a counterpart to residuated lattice? The answer is the mentioned EQ-algebra. Then the corresponding fuzzy logic has implication as a derived connective. This

logic [5, 6, 21] has, moreover a non-commutative strong conjunction and, consequently, unlike residuated lattice based non-commutative logics, one implication only. It should be emphasized that EQ-algebras are more general than residuated lattices. Namely that every residuated lattice is an EQ-algebra but not vice-versa.

One of the applications of mathematical fuzzy logic is the theory of intermediate quantifiers and their syllogisms. Informal analysis of them was provided by Peterson in the book [25]. Its formalization in the frame of *higher-order mathematical fuzzy logic* was suggested by Novák in [19] and further developed in many papers (see, e.g., [13, 14, 15, 16, 17] and others). In [23] we proved that all 105 valid syllogisms originally introduced in [25] are a consequence of only two algebraic inequalities and one equality. This result is obtained in a fuzzy type theory in which the algebra of truth values is an MV-algebra. In this paper we will show that this result is more general and, in fact, can be proved if we assume that the algebra of truth values is an involutive EQ-algebra (IEQ-algebra).

2 EQ-algebras

Definition 2.1. *A non-commutative EQ-algebra is an algebra*

$$\mathcal{E} = \langle E, \wedge, \otimes, \sim, \mathbf{1} \rangle \quad (1)$$

of type $(2, 2, 2, 0)$ fulfilling the following axioms for all $a, b, c \in E$:

- (E1) $\langle E, \wedge, \mathbf{1} \rangle$ is a commutative idempotent monoid (\wedge -semilattice with the top element $\mathbf{1}$). We put $a \leq b$ iff $a \wedge b = a$, as usual.
- (E2) $\langle E, \otimes, \mathbf{1} \rangle$ is a monoid such that \otimes is isotone w.r.t. \leq .
- (E3) $a \sim a = \mathbf{1}$, (reflexivity)
- (E4) $((a \wedge b) \sim c) \otimes (d \sim a) \leq c \sim (d \wedge b)$, (substitution)
- (E5) $(a \sim b) \otimes (c \sim d) \leq (a \sim c) \sim (b \sim d)$, (congruence)
- (E6) $(a \wedge b \wedge c) \sim a \leq (a \wedge b) \sim a$, (monotonicity)
- (E7) $a \otimes b \leq a \sim b$. (boundedness)

EQ-algebra is commutative if \otimes is commutative.

We put:

- $a \rightarrow b = (a \wedge b) \sim a$, (implication)
- If \mathcal{E} contains a bottom element $\mathbf{0}$ then $\neg a = a \sim \mathbf{0}$, (negation)
- $\tilde{a} = a \sim \mathbf{1}$.

Definition 2.2. *An EQ-algebra \mathcal{E} is:*

- *separated* if $a \sim b = \mathbf{1}$ implies $a = b$ for all $a, b \in E$. Then $a \sim b = \mathbf{1}$ if and only if $a = b$.
- *good* if $a \sim \mathbf{1} = a$ for all $a \in E$.
- *residuated* if $(a \otimes b) \wedge c = a \otimes b$ if and only if $a \wedge ((b \wedge c) \sim b) = a$ for all $a, b, c \in E$.

- involutive (IEQ-algebra) if $\neg\neg a = a$.
- complete if $\inf(K)$ exists for every $K \subseteq E$. Clearly, complete EQ-algebras are complete lattices.
- lattice ordered if it has also a binary operation \vee such that $\langle E, \wedge, \vee \rangle$ is a lattice.
- lattice EQ-algebra (ℓ EQ-algebra) if it is lattice ordered and the following additional substitution axiom holds $((a \vee b) \sim c) \otimes (d \sim a) \leq ((d \vee b) \sim c)$ for all $a, b, c, d \in E$.

Many properties of EQ-algebras were proved in the cited papers. Let us remind here only a few properties that hold in good EQ-algebras.

Lemma 2.3. *Let \mathcal{E} be a good EQ-algebra. Then the following holds for all $a, b, c \in E$.*

- (a) $a \leq (a \sim b) \sim b$,
- (b) $a \leq (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow b$,
- (c) $a \otimes (a \rightarrow b) \leq b$,
- (d) $a \rightarrow (b \rightarrow c) = b \rightarrow (a \rightarrow c)$.
- (e) $a \leq b \rightarrow c$ iff $b \leq a \rightarrow c$,
- (f) $\bigwedge_{i \in I} (a_i \rightarrow b) = \bigvee_{i \in I} a_i \rightarrow b$,
provided that both infimum as well as supremum exist.

Proof. See [7, 8]. □

In the rest of this paper, we assume that the algebra of truth values is a good, linearly ordered, complete IEQ-algebra.

3 Intermediate quantifiers and their syllogisms

For the definition of intermediate quantifiers we need the following:

- (i) The concept of *evaluative linguistic expression*, which are special expressions of natural language such as “very deep, roughly big, more or less good”, etc. Formalization of their semantics was developed in [20]. For this paper, it is enough to take them as special formulas of type oo (i.e., they are interpreted as fuzzy sets on on the set of truth values). We will consider evaluative expressions $Bi \Delta$ (“big”), $Bi Ex$ (“extremely big”), $Bi Ve$ (“very big”) and $\neg Sm$ (“not small”).
- (ii) The operation *cut of a fuzzy set* $y \in Form_{o\alpha}$ w.r.t. a fuzzy set $z \in Form_{o\alpha}$:

$$y|z \equiv \lambda x_\alpha \cdot zx \ \& \ \Delta(\Upsilon(zx) \Rightarrow (yx \equiv zx)). \quad (2)$$

Interpretation of this formula in a model is the following: for given fuzzy sets $B, Z \subseteq M$, $B|Z$ is a “cut” of B such that $(B|Z)(m) = Z(m)$ if there is such m , otherwise $(B|Z)(m) = 0$, $m \in M$. If there is no such m then $B|Z = \emptyset$. We can thus take various fuzzy sets Z to “pick up proper elements from B ” (together with their membership degrees).

- (iii) Measure $\mu \in \text{Form}_{o(o\alpha)(o\alpha)}$. A compound formula $(\mu B)A$ is interpreted as a measure of a fuzzy set A w.r.t. the fuzzy set B .

Definition 3.1. Let $Ev \in \text{Form}_{oo}$ be a formula representing some evaluative linguistic expression, $z \in \text{Form}_{o\alpha}$, $x \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ be variables and $A, B \in \text{Form}_{o\alpha}$ be formulas where B represents a measurable fuzzy set. An intermediate quantifier is one of the following formulas:

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x_{\alpha})(B_{o\alpha}, A_{o\alpha}) \equiv (\exists z)[(\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))], \quad (3)$$

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\exists} x_{\alpha})(B_{o\alpha}, A_{o\alpha}) \equiv (\exists z)[(\exists x)((B|z)x \wedge Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))]. \quad (4)$$

Either of the quantifiers (3) or (4) construes the sentence

$$\langle \text{Quantifier} \rangle B' \text{ s are } A \quad (5)$$

where $\langle \text{Quantifier} \rangle$ is a quantifier in a linguistic form.

Note that in this definition, we replaced cardinality of a fuzzy set (originally suggested by Zadeh in [28]) by its measure. Formula $B_{o\alpha}$ in (i)–(iii) represents a *universe of quantification*.

Definition 3.2. Let N be a set and $A, B \in \mathcal{F}(N)$. Let us denote by $F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z)$ interpretation of the formula $Ev((\mu B)(B|z))$. Then a semantic interpretation of the intermediate quantifiers (3) and (4) are truth values given by the respective formulas

$$Q_{Ev}^{\forall}(B, A) = \bigvee \left\{ \bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow A(u)) \wedge F_{Ev}^R(S, S|Z) \mid Z \in \mathcal{F}(N) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{Ev}^{\exists}(B, A) = \bigvee \left\{ \bigvee_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \wedge A(u)) \wedge F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) \mid Z \in \mathcal{F}(N) \right\}. \quad (7)$$

The measure and evaluation of the size of $B|Z$ is hidden in the function F_{Ev}^R . If we replace the metavariable Ev in (3) or (4) by a formula representing a specific evaluative linguistic expression then we obtain the following *algebraic representations* of the specific intermediate quantifiers.

Definition 3.3. (A) “All B ’s are A ”: $\bigwedge_{u \in N}(B(u) \rightarrow A(u))$,

(E) “No B ’s is A ”: $\bigwedge_{u \in N}(B(u) \rightarrow \neg A(u))$,

(P) “Almost all B ’s are A ”: $\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow A(u)) \wedge F_{BiEx}^R(B, B|Z))$,

(B) “Almost all B ’s are not A ”: $\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow \neg A(u)) \wedge F_{BiEx}^R(B, B|Z))$,

(T) “Most B ’s are A ”: $\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow A(u)) \wedge F_{BiVe}^R(B, B|Z))$,

(D) “Most B ’s are not A ”: $\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow \neg A(u)) \wedge F_{BiVe}^R(B, B|Z))$,

(K) “Many B ’s are A ”: $\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow A(u)) \wedge F_{\neg Sm}^R(B, B|Z))$,

(G) “Many B ’s are not A ”: $\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow \neg A(u)) \wedge F_{\neg Sm}^R(B, B|Z))$,

(I) “Some B ’s are A ”: $\bigvee_{u \in N}(B(u) \wedge A(u))$,

(O) “Some B ’s are not A ”: $\bigvee_{u \in N}(B(u) \wedge \neg A(u))$.

We will denote various kinds of quantifiers by $Q_X(B, A)$ where $X \in \{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{P}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{T}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{O}\}$.

4 Algebraic analysis of valid intermediate syllogisms

4.1 Formalization of syllogisms

A *syllogism* is a triple of formulas $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{C}$ where \mathcal{P}_1 and \mathcal{P}_2 are *major and minor premises* and \mathcal{C} is a *conclusion*. Let $Q_{\mathcal{P}_1}, Q_{\mathcal{P}_2}, Q_{\mathcal{C}}$ be quantifier symbols from (3) or (4) occurring in both premises and conclusion, respectively, and S, P, M be formulas representing properties of elements. The formula S is a *subject*, P is a *predicate* and M is a *middle formula*. As usual, syllogisms are gathered into the following four figures:

Figure I	Figure II	Figure III	Figure IV
$Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} M \text{ are } P$	$Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} P \text{ are } M$	$Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} M \text{ are } P$	$Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} P \text{ are } M$
$Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} S \text{ are } M$	$Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} S \text{ are } M$	$Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} M \text{ are } S$	$Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} M \text{ are } S$
$Q_{\mathcal{C}} S \text{ are } P$			

If all $Q_{\mathcal{P}_1}, Q_{\mathcal{P}_2}, Q_{\mathcal{C}} \in \{\forall, \exists\}$ then the corresponding syllogism is classical.

We say that it is *valid* if

$$T^{\text{IQ}} \vdash \mathcal{P}_1 \& \mathcal{P}_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}. \quad (8)$$

By the completeness theorem, syllogism (8) is valid iff

$$\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{P}_1) \otimes \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{P}_2) \leq \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{C}) \quad (9)$$

holds in any model $\mathcal{M} \models T^{\text{IQ}}$. Validity of (8) for all syllogisms presented in [?] was proven syntactically in [13, 15].

4.2 Fundamental algebraic inequalities

In the rest of this paper, we consider a complete IEQ-algebra \mathcal{E} .

Theorem 4.1 ([7], Theorem 3). *Let Ψ be an inequality in the language of EQ-algebras. Let $\bar{\Psi}$ be an inequality obtained from Ψ by replacing all occurrences of \otimes by its reverse $\bar{\otimes}$. Then Ψ is universally valid iff $\bar{\Psi}$ is valid.*

By this theorem, we may consider the inequalities presented below from one side of $\bar{\otimes}$ only.

Lemma 4.2. *Let $a, b, c \in E$. Then the following relations hold true:*

- (a) $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes (a \rightarrow b) \leq a \rightarrow c$,
- (b) $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes (a \wedge b) \leq a \wedge c$,
- (c) $(a \rightarrow b) = (\neg b \rightarrow \neg a)$,

Proof. (a) was proved in [22], Theorem 1(c) and in [7], Lemma 2(c) and Lemma 6(k).

(b) was proved in [22], Proposition 1 and Lemma 10(d).

(c) follows from [7], Lemma 7(a). □

The following inequalities are consequences of the previous lemma.

Lemma 4.3. *Let $a, b, c, d, f \in E$. Then*

- (a) *Let $a \otimes b \leq c$. Then $a \otimes (b \wedge f) \leq c \wedge f$,*

- (b) $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes ((a \rightarrow b) \wedge f) \leq (a \rightarrow c) \wedge f$,
- (c) $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes a \otimes (a \rightarrow b) \leq a \wedge c$,
- (d) $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes b \otimes (b \rightarrow a) \leq a \wedge c$,
- (e) $((b \rightarrow c) \wedge f) \otimes b \otimes (b \rightarrow a) \leq a \wedge c$,
- (f) $((b \rightarrow c)) \otimes b \otimes ((b \rightarrow a) \wedge f) \leq a \wedge c$,
- (g) $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes a \otimes ((a \rightarrow b) \wedge f) \leq a \wedge c$,
- (h) $((b \rightarrow c) \wedge f) \otimes a \otimes ((a \rightarrow b) \wedge f') \leq a \wedge c$,
- (i) $\neg\neg a = a$.
- (j) $((b \rightarrow c) \wedge f) \otimes ((b' \rightarrow a) \wedge f') \otimes (b \otimes b') \leq a \wedge c$.
- (k) $a \vee \bigvee_{j \in J} b_j = \bigvee_{j \in J} (a \vee b_j)$.

Proof. (a) follows from the properties of semilattice and (E2).

(b) is a consequence of (a) and Lemma 4.2(a).

(c) By Lemmas 2.3(c), 4.2(a) and (E2) we obtain $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes a \otimes (a \rightarrow b) \leq a \otimes (a \rightarrow c) \leq c, a$ and, hence, we obtain $(b \rightarrow c) \otimes a \otimes (a \rightarrow b) \leq a \wedge c$.

(d) Let us denote the left-hand side of (d) by L . Then it is a consequence of Lemma 4.2(b), the properties of good EQ-algebra and the properties of semilattice. Indeed, we have $L \leq (b \rightarrow c) \otimes a \leq a$ as well as $L \leq (b \rightarrow a) \otimes c \leq c$ which gives $L \leq a \wedge c$.

(e) and (f) are consequences of (d).

(g) is a consequence of (c) and general properties of good EQ-algebras.

(h) is a consequence of (g).

(i) holds in each IEQ-algebra.

(j) As a consequence of (d), we have

$$((b \rightarrow c) \wedge f) \otimes b \otimes ((b \rightarrow a) \wedge f') \leq a \wedge c,$$

as well as

$$((b' \rightarrow c) \wedge f) \otimes b' \otimes ((b' \rightarrow a) \wedge f') \leq a \wedge c.$$

From both inequalities, using (E2) and the inequality $r \otimes s \leq r \wedge s \leq r, s$ we obtain (j).

(k) $a \leq \bigvee_{j \in J} (a \vee b_j)$ as well as $\bigvee_{j \in J} b_j \leq \bigvee_{j \in J} (a \vee b_j)$ from which we conclude that $a \vee \bigvee_{j \in J} b_j \leq \bigvee_{j \in J} (a \vee b_j)$. Conversely, from $b_j \leq \bigvee_{j \in J} b_j$ we conclude that $\bigvee_{j \in J} (a \vee b_j) \leq \bigvee_{j \in J} (a \vee \bigvee_{j \in J} b_j) = a \vee \bigvee_{j \in J} b_j$. \square

In the sequel, we will consider properties M, S, P . In fact, they are determined by a context (or a possible world) in which they are used. For simplicity, however, we will take them as simple fuzzy sets in some universe.

Lemma 4.4. *Let U be a universe and $M, S, P \subseteq N$ be properties of elements of N .*

- (a) *Inequality $(m \rightarrow p) \otimes (s \rightarrow m) \leq s \rightarrow p$ of Lemma 4.2(a) implies validity of syllogism (AAA-I), whose algebraic form is*

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow P(u)).$$

- (b) Inequality $(m \rightarrow p) \otimes ((s \rightarrow m) \wedge f) \leq (s \rightarrow p) \wedge f$ of Lemma 4.3(b) implies validity of syllogism (**APP-I**), whose algebraic form is

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right) \leq \bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right).$$

- (c) Inequality $(m \rightarrow p) \otimes s \otimes (s \rightarrow m) \leq s \wedge p$ of Lemma 4.3(c) implies validity of syllogism (**A*AI-I**), whose algebraic form is

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigvee_{u \in N} S(u) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge P(u)).$$

- (d) Inequality $(m \rightarrow p) \otimes s \otimes ((s \rightarrow m) \wedge f) \leq s \wedge p$ of Lemma 4.3(g) implies validity of syllogism (**A*PI-I**), whose algebraic form is

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} \left(\bigvee_{u \in U} (S|Z)(u) \otimes \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right) \right) \leq \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge P(u)).$$

- (e) Inequality $(m \rightarrow p) \otimes (s \wedge m) \leq s \wedge p$ of Lemma 4.2(b) implies validity of syllogism (**AII-I**), whose algebraic form is

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge M(u)) \leq \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge P(u)).$$

Proof. Ad (a): We start with the following instance of Lemma 4.2(a):

$$(M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq S(u) \rightarrow P(u),$$

where $u \in N$. By the properties of infimum and monotonicity of \otimes we have

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)).$$

From both inequalities, using again the properties of infimum we obtain

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow P(u)). \quad (10)$$

Ad (b): We begin with the following instance of Lemma 4.3(b):

$$(M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes (((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z)) \leq ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z).$$

Similarly as in (a) we have

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right) \leq \\ (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z).$$

Joining these two inequalities and using the properties of supremum, we obtain

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right) \leq \\ \bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right).$$

Again, using the properties of supremum we obtain

$$\bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right) \leq \\ \bigvee_{Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)} \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right),$$

and using Lemma 4.3(k) we obtain (b).

Ad (c): We begin with the following instance of Lemma 4.3(c):

$$(M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes S(u) \otimes (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq (S(u) \wedge P(u)).$$

Then

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes S(u) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes S(u) \otimes (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq \\ \bigvee_{u \in N} (\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes S(u) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u))) = \\ \bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \bigvee_{u \in N} S(u) \otimes \bigwedge_{u \in N} (S(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \leq \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge P(u)),$$

using properties of supremum and Lemma 4.3(k).

(d) To prove **(A*PI-I)**, we start with syllogism **(A*AI-I)** and apply Lemma 4.3(g) to obtain the following provable inequality for any $Z \subsetneq N$:

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes \\ \left(\bigvee_{u \in N} (S|Z)(u) \otimes \left(\bigwedge_{u \in N} ((S|Z)(u) \rightarrow M(u)) \wedge F_{Bi\ Ex}^R(S, S|Z) \right) \right) \rightarrow \\ \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge P(u)).$$

From this, taking supremum over all $Z \in \mathcal{F}(N)$, using the properties of supremum and Lemma 4.3(k) we obtain (d).

Ad (e): We begin with the following instance of Lemma 4.2(b):

$$(M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes (S(u) \wedge M(u)) \leq (S(u) \wedge P(u)).$$

From it we prove that

$$\bigwedge_{u \in N} (M(u) \rightarrow P(u)) \otimes (S(u) \wedge M(u)) \leq \bigvee_{u \in N} (S(u) \wedge P(u)),$$

for all $u \in N$. Then, using the properties of supremum and Lemma 4.3(k) we obtain inequality (e), i.e., syllogism (**AII-I**).

□

From the previous lemma follows validity of syllogisms (**AAP-I**), (**AAT-I**), (**AAK-I**), (**APT-I**), (**APK-I**), (**AKK-I**), (**ATT-I**) and (**ATK-I**) (**A*KI-I**) and (**A*TI-I**). The proof of validity of the other syllogisms is similar. Thus, the following theorem holds true.

Theorem 4.5. *All valid syllogisms with intermediate quantifiers formulated in EQ-algebra based fuzzy type theory are the consequence of two inequalities and one equality of Lemma 4.2.*

Similar theorem has been proved in [23] for the case that the formal system is MV-algebra based fuzzy type theory. The theorem above is more general since MV-algebras are special EQ-algebras. From our results we conclude that human syllogistic reasoning that uses even non-precisely defined properties is based on fundamental algebraic properties of ordered structures without other special assumptions.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we introduced the concept of EQ-algebra and a special theory of intermediate quantifiers based on the EQ-algebra fuzzy type theory. We proved that human syllogistic reasoning has more general roots and does not depend on special properties of the used algebra of truth values. Namely, we proved that validity of intermediate syllogisms is based on two fundamental algebraic inequalities and one equality, that are valid already in very general IEQ-algebras. The paper is a contribution to the concept of Fuzzy Natural Logic.

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